

THE LEVELS PREDICTING THE DEATH ANXIETY OF LONELINESS AND MEANING IN LIFE IN YOUTH

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Abstract:

This study aims to examine whether variables of loneliness and meaning in life significantly predict death anxiety in youth attending university and those who have graduated from university. The research is a descriptive study and is designed in the relational survey model. This study constitutes of 239 volunteer participants, including 103 females (103%) and 136 males (56.91%) who were selected by simple random sampling from youth participating in the Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University in 2019. The age range of the study group was 20-36 years, and the mean age was 23.66 years. Data collection tools are Abdel-Khalek Death Anxiety Scale, Meaning of Life Scale, UCLA Loneliness Scale and Personal Data Form. Descriptive statistics, Pearson Moments Multiplication Correlation Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were used. In this study, loneliness in youth and meaning in life significantly predicted the death anxiety; there was a positive and meaningful relationship between death anxiety and loneliness, and a negative relationship was found between death anxiety and meaning in life. In addition, it was determined that, while death anxiety varied significantly depending on gender, the levels of meaning in life and loneliness did not differ significantly according to gender. It was determined that the majority of young people suffered at least one loss in the form of the death of a relative; there was not a significant difference in meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness according to level of loss. In the study, it was found differed significantly levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness depending on the state of being uncomfortable talking about death.

Keywords: Youth, anxiety of death, loneliness, meaning in life

1. Introduction

Although the phenomenon of death is considered to be the inevitable end of normal life, it is sometimes evaluated by individuals along with conditions defined as negative as

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well as fear and anxiety or their results associated with psychopathology. To know the nature of death anxiety in young people and to understand the related variables, the counseling studies can be important in terms of configuring the psychological support studies to be presented for many problems experienced during this period, especially on death anxiety.

According to Freud (1918), *“the wars in the world and the mass deaths of thousands of people as a result of these wars make it difficult to deny death and compel individuals to believe in death. Although individuals try to deny death, it is seen that death has become undeniable by various events in life. Therefore, the phenomenon of death arises directly or indirectly with confronting death in different ways and at the forefront of concerns that directly or indirectly, consciously or unconsciously individuals of all ages are aware of or suppressed (as cited in Derin, 2019).*

1.1. Death Anxiety

Death is universal and can cause anxiety in any human beings (Kübler-Ross, 1997). Death is also a symbol of a great concern about an individual's absence from existence, and in this respect, a symbol of a fundamental and relentless concern that explains the essence of human existence (Kastenbaum, 2007). Each individual has a similar concern over death, while at the same time shares a common destiny in this respect (Kübler-Ross, 1997). It refers to the anxiety and fear of an individual about death (Carpenito-Moyet, 2013). The anxiety of death manifests itself in many things, ranging from dreams to defense mechanisms, from internal conflicts to the emergence of social structures, religions and ideologies in individuals (Yalom, 2014). In addition, the presence of death and awareness of it contributes to individual such as enjoying life (Kastenbaum, 2007).

According to Belsky (1999), death anxiety includes fear, thoughts, fears and emotions about death. Yalom (2014) emphasizes that fear of death is the basis of death anxiety and that everyone will experience fear of death; the fear of death represents the fear of extinction, and the fear of death represents the concrete belief that death is frightening (Lehto & Stein, 2009). Death anxiety is an unsettling situation that arises as a result of an individual thinking about the death of himself or others, has an existential origin and stems from multidimensional concerns (Nyatanga & Vocht, 2006). Even in approaches emphasizing that death anxiety is a multidimensional structure, it is emphasized the reality of death is emotional, cognitive and motivational elements, that it arouses fear and anxiety about its prediction and awareness and varies according to its stages of development and socio-cultural life formations (Lehto & Stein, 2009).

Considering the theories regarding death anxiety; Freud (1992) believes that death anxiety originates from guilt or sudden thoughts in the child emerging as a result of psychodynamic vision, death anxiety, oedipal conflicts and separation anxiety; that superego is the most important concern ever been experienced. He emphasizes in his theory of *“instincts of life and death”* that the purpose of life is death. According to Jung (2006), the fear of death of an individual actually comes from fear of life; fear of death means fear of life. When an individual realizes that what he has, his desires, and endeavors will gradually disappear, he begins to fear. Horney (1980) argues that people

may feel death due to negative events in life, and that this desire, combined with the fear of death, has become an uncertain concern.

From an existential point of view, death is inevitable, it is within life, so the anxiety of death also envelops every human being. In general, existential theories accept death as a symbol of the fundamental anxiety that explains the essence of an individual's existence. In this respect, it is accepted that the anxiety of death is an inevitable anxiety that is deep in the self of all of us and which is experienced before reaching the level of consciousness of the individual (Geçtan, 1990). According to Yalom (2014), the individual is concerned about certain facts such as death, freedom, existential isolation and meaninglessness, and death is the first source of psychopathology. Death is the greatest dilemma that people have, one can choose death if one wants to, but death will die even if one does not want to. Therefore, death is the greatest mystery that existence cannot solve, but individual has to live, and perhaps that is hidden within the meaning of life. The existence of death anxiety is related to the behavior of escaping death and enmity of it; the way to deal with and get rid of the anxiety of death is to face death, to recognize death and to know it.

In Cognitive Theory, death anxiety is addressed as other anxiety problems. It has been suggested that death anxiety has an important role in other anxiety disorders (Furer & Walker, 2008). The anxiety that arises naturally in the face of danger just as an alarm system is not only an aspect that protects the individual, but also it can turn into a disorder that is a life-impairing disorder that negatively affects an individual's behavior (Riskind, 2015). This transformation of anxiety is closely related to the meaning that the individual puts in danger. The uncertainty of time when the danger will come further increases this anxiety. In this respect, anxiety is more a feeling of future-oriented than "present". The majority of individuals with anxiety are concerned about death and often think they die (Beck, 2005). In addition, it is argued that death anxiety develops as a result of negative thoughts acquired by the individual regarding death (Tanhan, 2007).

Kübler Ross's approach to death (1997) is as follows: *"Rapid technological advancement and new scientific achievements have not only served man to acquire new skills, but also developed weapons of mass destruction that increased the fear of a terrifying and destructive death. Human beings have to psychologically protect themselves against this growing fear of death, the state of uncertainty and desperation to take precautions. Psychologically, they can be able to revel in their own death for a while. We cannot imagine our own death in our subconscious, and we believe in our immortality, but we do not have any trouble understanding the death of our neighbor, the news of people dying on highways, in a war, and this fact supports our belief in immortality in our subconscious, and it allows us to rejoice and say in the secret world of our subconscious: "Someone else, not me."* Ross mentions that, since an individual has nothing to do with death, an individual may feel hatred and anger in the event of death, or alleviate this situation through various rituals and ceremonies in accordance with his or her religious requirements.

In studies on death anxiety; it is indicated that death anxiety is low in individuals who think they are living a meaningful life (Chow, 2017), who have quality of life (Adeeb, Saleem, Kynat, Tufail & Zaffar, 2017), and who have a level of happiness (Gesser, Wong

& Reker, 1988). It is stated that death anxiety decreases in individuals who have a positive attitude towards life (Azarian, Aghakhani & Ashuri, 2016). On the other hand, it is indicated that high levels of death is associated with pessimism (Barnett, Anderson & Marsden, 2018), despair (Gesser, et. al., 1988); loneliness (Chow, 2017), low perception of social support (Adeeb, et. al., 2017) inability to get enough from life (Yalom, 2014).

Death anxiety has also been shown to be associated with various psychopathologies. In these studies, the relationship has been found between death anxiety and anxiety, somatization and phobic avoidance responses (Erdogdu & Ozkan, 2007), agoraphobic symptoms (Foa, Steketee & Young, 1984), eating disorders and anorexia neurosis (Alantar & Maner, 2008). In this respect, defining the mental problems of youth and determining the mental health needs of young people can contribute to the study of death anxiety.

1.2. University Youth

While the university period falls on approximately 17-25 years of age, it is an important period as the end of adolescence and the transition to first adulthood. According to Jung, university students are in their youth and have many responsibilities to fulfill as an individual during this period. These include: to gain a place in the outside world, to make professional decisions, to have marriage and children, to develop social harmony (as cited in Hall & Nordby, 2016). This period Erikson refers to psychosocial procrastination and prolonged adolescence (as cited in Arnett, 2004). According to Erikson, in industrialized societies, individuals have prolonged adolescence, and therefore, experience psychosocial moratorium. In the theory of emerging adulthood, while Arnett (2000) considers the period from the end of adolescence (18 years old) to the early thirties as emerging adulthood, he suggests that emerging adulthood is a different period of development from both adolescence and adulthood with its own characteristics. In this process, individuals experience the most important turning points in their lives, get rid of their dependence in education and work, and prepare for adulthood and become independent individuals (Tanner, 2006).

Arnett (2004) speaks of five peculiar features of emerging adulthood. These include: A period of search for identity, and the emerging adults continue to seek identity in the dimensions of romantic relationships, business and philosophy of life. This period is a period of instability and in this context, instabilities can be experienced such as job changes, starting and finishing a romantic relationship and changing homes. In addition, during this period, individuals are self-focused, have to make decisions on their own, make their own decisions, gain competence towards life and learn to stand on their own. The other feature is that this period is a period of infinite possibilities. The final feature of emerging adulthood is that individuals in this age range feel caught in the middle; individuals seem to go back and forth between adolescent and adulthood. It is stated that young people in the university period experienced a transition period with a variability involving various experiments, change and discovery in search of identity (Arnett, 2000). Studies conducted in Turkey indicate that individuals between the ages of 19 and 26 living in the city are in the period of adulthood (Atak & Çok, 2015). Based on these

explanations, it seems important to focus on the concerns and spiritual needs of young people for the university period and post-university period, which are considered as important steps for the transition to adulthood roles, followed by processes such as completing education, settling in a permanent job, becoming independent of the family, getting married and having children.

1.3. Death Anxiety in Youth

While the phenomenon of death is evaluated differently according to the developmental periods; self-centeredness in adolescence affects the way the young people look at death. Adolescent's belief in his own personal uniqueness can turn into the belief that he will never die, and consequently, in the face of a loss, adolescents can develop strong emotional responses such as denial, anger, feelings of blame and sadness (Wass, 2003). Adults tend to see death as a blow and injustice to their selves, which prevents them from enjoyment and responsibility. When adults review their lives, they evaluate not based on how long they have lived, but on how much time they have left; with the transition to middle age, it is felt more clearly than ever that death is inevitable (Osarchuk & Tatz, 1993).

In studies conducted on death anxiety, it is accepted that young people do not think much about death because they are still far from death and do not talk to their families about it; with the age, individuals start to think more about death and the elderly feel closer to death (Mudau, 2012). However, studies have shown that young people have higher levels of death anxiety than elderly people. In a comparative study, adolescent, middle-aged and elderly individuals' death anxiety levels related to the death of themselves and others were examined, and it was determined that young people (13-20 years of age) had significantly higher death anxiety than individuals in other groups (Amjad, 2014). Another study found that death anxiety in university students was significantly higher than that of the elderly (Reyes et. al., 2017); that death anxiety peaked in their 20s in both men and women, then decreased significantly. The reason for this is that individuals in their 20s do not often encounter death in their circles of friends and acquaintances, and the lack of death experience in their environment and the uncertainty of death may lead to higher death anxiety in young people (Robah, 2017). On the other hand, there are research results showing that death anxiety in the elderly is higher than that of young people (Erdoğdu & Özkan, 2007).

Many negative situations faced by young people in their university years can cause them to worry and experience despair; university life itself is seen to be an environment that creates anxiety and stress in general. During this period, it is known that students experience stress in many areas. It is observed that these problem areas arises in matters such as curriculum, faculty, environmental adaptation, lack of social, cultural, artistic and sporting activities, anxiety of the future, personal and family problems, insatiability, lack of physical conditions, undemocratic environment, aimlessness, intellectuality, administrative problems, (un)interest in politics, spiritual emptiness and lack of self-confidence (Şahin, Şahin Fırat, Zoraloğlu & Açıkgöz, 2009). In other studies, conducted on death anxiety in university students, it has been reported

that anxiety optimism is associated with variables such pessimism, physical health, mental health, happiness and level of satisfaction in life (Abdel-Khalek & Sábado, 2005), focus of audit and death obsession (Derin, 2019). It is seen frequently emphasized that university students need psychological help by facing various psychological problems.

Loneliness is described as emotional and social loneliness with the way it arises; emotional loneliness is a condition in which a person shows feelings of anxiety and emptiness, resulting from the lack of a close attachment to another person. Social loneliness, on the other hand, is associated with depression and distress, which involves social relations, resulting from the lack of social networking (Kılınc, 2005). Loneliness is mainly due to interpersonal barriers and miscommunication, when an individual sees people around him as a means of threatening, is highly concerned and is estranged from people (Yalom, 2009). It is also stated that loneliness increases vulnerability (Mushta, et. al., 2014) and isolation from the social environment, especially in young people in terms of problems such as depression (Cacioppo, Hughers, Waite, Hawkley & Thisted, 2006) and anxiety (Lykes & Kemmelmeier, 2014). In this context, the importance of a comprehensive examination of loneliness, which poses a risk to many problem areas, and the relationship between fear of death in university students is emphasized (Tomer & Eliason, 2000).

In line with the literature given above, when the results are evaluated holistically, it is considered that significantly higher levels of death anxiety in university student youth than in other age groups pose a risk in terms of the mental health and psychological assistance needs of these young people. Therefore, it is inevitable that university students need psychological assistance in different subjects during this period. As a matter of fact, it is clear that studies are needed when considering the problems and psychosocial needs of young people in different fields. In this respect, examining the relationship of death anxiety with different variables in young university students who are both developmentally in transition and facing many concerns and problems may contribute to the studies to be conducted on this subject in the future. In addition, knowing the nature of death anxiety in university students may be important in terms of creating an effective psychological assistance process for counselors who are experiencing high death anxiety during psychological counseling with the individual or group to be conducted.

1.4. Purpose of the Research

The aim of this study is to investigate whether the loneliness and meaning in life levels of young people predicted death anxiety significantly.

1.4.1. Problem Statement of the Research

Does the loneliness in young people and meaning in life predict the death anxiety significantly?

The research questions to be answered for this purpose are as follows:

- 1) Is there a significant difference in young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness level according to gender?

- 2) Is there a significant difference in young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness according to experience of loss?
- 3) Is there a significant difference in young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness according to their state of being uncomfortable with talking about death?
- 4) Is there a significant relationship between young people's levels of anxiety of death, meaning in life and levels of loneliness?
- 5) Do the young people's levels of loneliness and meaning in life predict their death anxiety significantly?

2. Method

The research is a descriptive study and is designed in the relational survey model. This study aims to examine whether variables of loneliness and meaning in life significantly predict death anxiety in young people attending university and those who have graduated from university.

2.1. Study Group of the Research

This study constitutes of 239 volunteer participants, including 103 females (103%) and 136 males (56.91%) who were selected by simple random sampling from students in the University in 2019. While 210 (83.07%) of the young people in the study group were in the 4th grade in different undergraduate programs, 29 (16.3%) of them graduated from an undergraduate program. The age range of the study group was 20-36 years, and the mean age was 23.66 years.

2.2. Data Collection Tools

2.2.1. Abdel-Khalek Death Anxiety Scale

The scale was developed in Arabic and English by Abdel-Khalek in 2004 (19). Consisting of 20 items and 5 factors, the scale employs five-item Likert (1=none and 5=too much). The Cronbach Alpha Value, calculated as 0.86 for the Turkish form of the Abdel-Khalek Death Anxiety Scale, shows that the scale has high internal consistency. Original reliability study for the scale was conducted in Syria, Kuwait and Egypt; Cronbach Alpha values were found as 0.89, 0.93 and 0.90 respectively (Sarıççek Aydoğan, Gülseren, Öztürk Sarıkaya & Özen, 2015). Within the scope of this study, Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated as 0.81.

2.2.2. Meaning of Life Scale (MLS)

The scale was developed by Steger, Frazier, Oishi and Kaler (2006). As a result of the exploratory factor analysis, it was observed that the scale consisted of 10 substances and a two-dimensional structure; these substances accounted for 68.2% of the total variance. Factor loads of the scale were ranked between .65 and .88, and the total correlation coefficients of matter were between .44 and .78. The internal consistency of the MLS was found to be .81 and .85 for each subscale, respectively. As a result of the test and re-test,

these values were determined as .72 and .76, respectively. These findings show that the Turkish form of MLS is a valid and reliable measuring tool (Demirdağ & Kalafat, 2015). Within the scope of this study, Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated as 0.83.

2.2.3. UCLA Loneliness Scale (UCLA-LS)

The scale was developed by Russell, Peplau and Ferguson (1978). The scale, prepared in 4-item Likert type, consists of 20 expressions that reflect how lonely people define their experiences. In a study conducted by Demir, Cronbach's Alpha internal consistency coefficient was calculated as 0.96. Test-retest reliability coefficient of the scale, which was carried out in a five-week interval, was found as 0.94. While the individual receives the opposite of what he or she marked in questions no.1, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 15, 16, 20; the highest score is 80, and the lowest score is 20 (Demir, 1989). Within the scope of this study, Cronbach's Alpha value was calculated as 0.86.

2.2.4. Personal Data Form

The form was developed to retrieve information about demographic characteristics of the young people involved in the study. The personal information form contains information about gender, age, ongoing licensing program, status of loss of relatives, who they have lost, and whether they are uncomfortable talking about death.

2.3. Analysis of Data

Descriptive statistics were used for the data analysis in the study; t test was used for two independent samples; Pearson Moments Multiplication Correlation Analysis and Multiple Regression Analysis were used.

3. Findings

In this section, descriptive findings of the study are first given descriptive statistics, and finally the findings were given with regard to the intervariable relationship.

Table 1 contains data on the scales used in the research, including the lowest and highest score, arithmetic mean, standard deviation, distortion and flattening values.

Table 1: The Lowest And Highest Score, Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation, Distortion And Flattening Values

Variables	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Ss	Skewness	Kurtosis
Death Anxiety	10.00	77.00	35.8410	17.90732	-.087	-1.145
Loneliness	12.00	65.00	41.7406	13.00160	-1.031	-.216
Meaning in life	12.00	61.00	43.3808	8.50021	-.624	.817

N=237

Table 1 shows, Minimum and Maximum values, mean and standard deviation (Sd) and Skewness and Kurtosis values for the data collection tools used in the research. Accordingly, it was observed that the skewness and Kurtosis values varied between -.087 and -1.145 for death anxiety; between -1.031 and -.216 for loneliness, and between -.493

and .209 for meaning in life for data collected in the study. Kurtosis and Skewness values are considered to be normal distribution between -1.5 and +1.5 (Tabachnick and Fidell, 2013). Accordingly, the data of this study showed normal distribution, and therefore the analysis was continued with parametric techniques.

The distribution of the young people who make up the working group according to the undergraduate programs they are attending is included in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of Participants regarding the Undergraduate Programs They Attend

Undergraduate Program Attended	f	%
Theology	47	19.7
Turkish Language and Literature	45	18.8
Mathematics	35	14.6
History	31	13.0
English Language and Literature	16	6.7
Accounting and Financial Management	12	5.0
Public Administration	8	3.3
Management Information Systems	7	2.9
Business Administration	6	2.5
Archaeology	3	1.25
Total	210	87.86

In Table 2, young people's distribution as per their undergraduate programs can be seen.

3.1. Findings on Demographic Variables of the Study

3.1.1. Findings on the Analysis of Levels of Death Anxiety, Meaning in Life and Loneliness in Young People

The results of t-Test for Independent Samples to determine whether levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness in young people differ in terms of gender are given in Table 3.

Table 3: The Differentiation of Meaning in Life, Death Anxiety and Loneliness Levels by Gender

Variables	Gender	N	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	T	p
Meaning in Life	Female	103	35.92	12.71	1.85	-1.247	.214
	Male	136	38.23	13.45			
Death Anxiety	Yes	103	38.25	17.42	2.51	3.371	.001
	No	136	29.77	17.78			
Loneliness	Yes	103	41.92	2.71	1.86	.345	.730
	No	136	41.27	13.77			

p>.05 p>.01 N=139

As shown in Table 3, while death anxiety in young people varies significantly according to gender, mean death anxiety in women is found higher than that of men ($p>.01$). It can be observed that the levels of meaning and loneliness in life do not differ significantly in terms of gender ($p>.01$).

3.2. Distribution of State of Differentiation in Young People's Levels of Meaning in Life, Death Anxiety and Loneliness as per their Loss Experiences

When the distribution of the participants regarding their loss experiences is examined; the number of persons living losses is 161 (67.4%), and the number of those who have not experienced any losses is 78 (32.6%). The losses of those who answered as Yes were determined as follows: 43 participants lost their grandparents (18%); 22 participants lost their father's mother (13.4%); 20 participants lost their mother's mother (8.4%); 13 participants lost their siblings (5.4%); 10 participants lost their mother's brother (4.2%); 12 participants lost their father's brother (5.0%); 9 participants lost their friends; 9 participants lost their friends (3.8%); 7 participants lost their cousins (2.9%); 5 participants lost their mother's sister (2.1%); 4 participants lost their aunt's husband (1.7%); 3 participants lost their mothers (1.3%); 2 participants lost their father's sister (8%); and 2 participants lost their teachers (8%).

Findings on state of differentiation of young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness as per loss experience are given in Table 4.

As shown in Table 4, it is observed that levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness in university students do not differ significantly depending on whether or not they have a loss experience ($p>.01$).

Table 4: State of Differentiation of Young People's Levels of Meaning in Life, Death Anxiety and Loneliness as per Loss Experience

Variables	Loss Experience	N	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	T	<i>p</i>
Meaning in life	Yes	103	35.80	12.71		-1.342	.181
	No	136	38.20	13.34	12.71		
Death Anxiety	Yes	103	36.38	18.49		.685	.494
	No	136	34.68	16.65	18.49		
Loneliness	Yes	103	42.46	12.96	12.96	1.247	.214
	No	136	40.22	13.03			

$p>.05$ $p>.01$ N=139

Findings on state of differentiation of young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness as per being uncomfortable with talking about death are given in Table 5.

Table 5: Findings on State of Differentiation of Young People's Levels of Meaning in Life, Death Anxiety and Loneliness as per Being Uncomfortable with Talking about Death

Variables	Loss Experience	N	$\bar{X}$	Ss	Sd	T	p																				
Meaning in life	Yes	151	34.25	13.12	1.067	-3.007	.003																				
	No	75	39.64	11.70				Death Anxiety	Yes	151	40.77	16.35	1.331	5.698	.000	No	75	27.34	17.32	Loneliness	Yes	151	43.22	11.87	.966	2.261	.025
Death Anxiety	Yes	151	40.77	16.35	1.331	5.698	.000																				
	No	75	27.34	17.32				Loneliness	Yes	151	43.22	11.87	.966	2.261	.025	No	75	39.12	14.64								
Loneliness	Yes	151	43.22	11.87	.966	2.261	.025																				
	No	75	39.12	14.64																							

$p > .05$ $p > .01$ $N = 139$

As shown in Table 5, it was determined that young people's levels of death anxiety, meaning life, loneliness differ significantly as per their state of being uncomfortable with talking about death; that those who said "yes, I would be uncomfortable" were found to have higher average scores for death anxiety and loneliness than those who said "no". On the other hand, those who say "I am not bothered to talk about death" have higher levels of meaning in life than others ($p > .01$).

3.3. Correlations between Death Anxiety and Meaning in Life and Loneliness

Correlation analysis findings for the relationship between variables are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Correlations between Death Anxiety and Meaning in Life and Loneliness

Variables	Death Anxiety	Meaning in life	Loneliness
Death Anxiety	1		
Meaning in life	-.517**	1	
Loneliness	.359**	-.172**	1

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$

As shown in Table 6, while there is a negative and significant relationship is found between death anxiety and meaning in life ($r = -.517$, $p < .01$); a positive and significant relationship is found between loneliness and death anxiety ($r = .359$, $p < .01$). There is a negative and meaningful relationship between loneliness and meaning in life ($r = -.172$, $p < .01$).

3.4. Multiple Regression Analysis of the Level of Prediction of Loneliness and Meaning in Life for Death Anxiety in University Students

Multiple Regression Analysis findings on the level of prediction of loneliness and meaning in life for death anxiety in university students are presented in Table 7.

Table 7: Level of Prediction of Loneliness and Meaning in Life for Death Anxiety in University Students

Independent Variables						Durbin-Watson
	B	SH _B	B	t	P	
Constant	43.584	4.542		9.595	.000	1.685
Meaning in life	-.649	.074	-.469	-8.743	.000	
Loneliness	.383	.074	.278	5.186	.000	

R=.585, R²=.342 ΔR²=.336 F_(2; 236)= 61.294, p=.000

*p< .05; **p< .01

According to Table 7, it has been determined that the regression model established between dependent variable of the study, death anxiety, and independent variables of the study, loneliness and meaning in life, is appropriate [F_(2; 236)= 61.294; p< .01]; loneliness and meaning in life together explain around 34% of the change in death anxiety. When the t test results on the significance of regression coefficients is examined, it has been determined that meaning in life has a negative and significant effect on death anxiety [β=-.469; t=-8.743; p<.01], that loneliness has a positive and significant effect on death anxiety [β=.278; t=5.186; p<.01]. According to these results, death anxiety decreases in young people with high levels of meaning in life; death anxiety is high in young people with high levels of loneliness.

4. Discussion

This research was conducted to examine the level of prediction for young people's anxiety of death by variables of loneliness and meaning in life. The findings obtained as a result of the analysis are discussed in the light of the literature in the order given in the sub-problems of the research.

In the finding obtained for the first sub-problem of the study, it was revealed that death anxiety in young people differs significantly according to gender; the mean of death anxiety in women was higher than that of men. In studies comparing death anxiety in terms of gender in the literature, it is observed that women's death anxiety is significantly higher than that of men (Chow, 2017; Yukay-Yüksel, Güneş & Akdağ, 2017). It is emphasized that high death anxiety scores in women are more related to their tendency to report negative emotions more than men rather than death issues (Tang, Wu & Yan, 2002). It is also stated that the fact that women have different sociocultural experiences and conditions (Lehto & Stein, 2009) and their ability to express their feelings such as sadness, sorrow and fear more compared to men are effective in this process (Abdel-Khalek & Sabado, 2005). However, there are also studies reporting that men's death anxiety levels are higher than those of women (Halıcı Kurtulan & Kararımak, 2016). Based on these results, the difference of death anxiety in men and women can be interpreted as important in terms of evaluating gender as an important factor in studies to be conducted on death anxiety in young people.

Another finding of the study found that the levels of meaning in life did not differ significantly in terms of gender. While this finding is supported by some studies in the literature, there are also other studies with different results. Studies conducted by Steger and Kashdan (2007) and Demirbaş (2010) have also shown that the existence of meaning in life and the levels of seeking meaning in life do not differ significantly according to gender. On the other hand, there are studies revealing that meaning in life differs by gender (Steger, Frazier, Oishi & Kaler, 2006). In a study conducted by Demirbaş Çelik (2016), it was also found that the existence of meaning in life and levels of purpose in life in university students women are higher than that of men. When these results are evaluated in general, it is seen that examining the effect of gender on meaning in life may make an important contribution in this regard.

As another finding obtained in this study, it was determined that young people's levels of loneliness do not vary significantly by gender. In the field literature where loneliness is examined by gender, some studies indicate that there is no significant difference in the level of loneliness according to gender (Izgar, 2009), and there are studies with different results. In addition to the results showing that women's levels of loneliness are higher than those of men (Kutlu, 2005); there are also studies revealing that loneliness is higher in men (Deniz, Hamarta & Arı, 2005). Women and men's differences in situations related to loneliness, such as perceptions of social support and self-opening levels, as well as gender roles variables may be related in terms of findings different gender-related outcomes in levels of loneliness.

Regarding the second sub-problem of the study, it was examined whether young people differed significantly in their levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness, and in this context, it was primarily determined that young people had loss experiences. Regarding this result, it was determined that majority of the participants suffered at least one loss in the form of the death of a relative. Humphrey (2017) mentions frequent situations experienced in different ways such as in the form of loss of a loved one, loss of an item, moving, loss of an organ, migration, loss of a period of life etc. in the process of loss that remains in all periods of life. All these losses are real, and they bring along mourning (Spall & Callis, 1997). Although individuals react differently to losses according to their developmental periods, usually sadness, desperation, anger, crying are common (Scheeringa, Peebles, Cook & Zeanah, 2001). In this respect, knowing the loss experience of young people may be important in terms of understanding effects of young people's loss experiences on their levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness. In another finding related to the second sub-problem of the study, it was determined that university students' levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness did not vary as per state of having a loss experience. While the reactions of individuals vary according to developmental, relational, loss type and the form of loss experience in the face of losses; they often force individuals to cope with negative emotions. It is very important for young people that these reactions do not turn into pathological results (Humphrey, 2017). That is because it is indicated that trauma and loss experiences in individuals (e.g., war and other traumas, traffic accidents) increase death anxiety (Abdel-Khalek, 2004). In addition, it is indicated that those who have witnessed the death of a relative (Yukay-

Yuksel, et. al., 2017), those with traumatic experiences (Tolstikova, Flemin & Chartier, 2005) are more likely to have death anxiety. It is emphasized that having a smaller social network and experiencing a recent loss are among the risk factors associated with loneliness (Hawkley & Cacioppo, 2007). However, according to the findings obtained in this study, the lack of differentiation in young people's levels of death, meaning in life and loneliness according to the state of loss does not reveal the cause and effect relationship between these variables. Therefore, it is thought that further studies are needed to demonstrate the effects of loss experiences. Accordingly, it will be important to understand the role of young people's loss experiences in understanding young people's levels of anxiety of death, meaning in life and loneliness.

In the third sub-problem of the study, it was examined whether there was a significant difference in young people's levels of meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness depending on state of being uncomfortable talking about death, and it was determined that young young people's levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness varied significantly as per state of being uncomfortable talking about death. Accordingly, it was determined that, while levels of death anxiety and loneliness were significantly higher for those who were uncomfortable talking about death, their levels of meaning in life were low. This condition is considered to be that young people with high levels of death anxiety and loneliness but low in meaning in life avoid talking about death. Death anxiety has a very complex relationship with dimensions such as fear of uncertainty, fear of loneliness, fear of losing relatives, fear of losing a sense of identity, fear of postmortem punishment, fear of losing control, fear of pain, fear of losing your body and fear of extinction (Karaca, 2000). Thorson and Powell (1988) indicate that individuals also express their disheartened deep thoughts and emotions about their own death by means of dimensions such as denial of death, fear of death, avoidance of death, and reluctance to interact with a dying person (Lonetto & Templer, 1986). It may not be easy for an individual to talk about this subject that causes the utmost pain, fear or anxiety. In this process, the individual may be uncomfortable talking about this subject because he or she is suffering from a loss or in relation to death anxiety. This is very important for understanding the difficulty of young people talking about death. In particular, university students in the mourning process are under the risk of suppressing or denying their emotions towards their loss because of the anxiety that their reactions may not be understood and their friends from university may have negative feelings and thoughts about them (Gizir, 2006). On the other hand, although it is emphasized that many people tend to accept the damages when they talk to someone in the process of mourning and loss (McCoyd, Walter & Lopez Levers, 2012); young people's refusal to talk about death seems explanatory in terms of reflecting their efforts both to cope with death anxiety and loneliness, as well as to seek meaning in life.

The study also found that those who are uncomfortable talking about death have significantly higher levels of loneliness. Here, there may be an avoidance of facing or talking by individual with the effect of the sense of extinction and nothingness created by the phenomenon of death. The death of a person is very difficult in terms of dealing with situations such as suffering of the people left behind, the painful process of death,

the uncertainty of life after death, the fact that the person will no longer have any experiences, and these are among the causes of death anxiety (Yalom, 2009). Loss can also mean loss of social support and becoming lonely for the individual. Loneliness includes optimistic/ pessimistic comments by individuals that create lack of interpersonal relationships and subjective assessments of whether the state of loneliness will pass over time (De Jong Gierveld & Van Tilburg, 2006). While loneliness is treated as a danger to psychological, physical and social integrity of a person, which causes pain and distress to that person (Kozaklı, 2006); this is often accompanied by negative emotions that involve emotional experiences such as sadness, sorrow, guilt, shame, frustration, despair (De Jong Gierveld & Van Tilburg, 2006). In this context, young people with high scores of loneliness tend to talk less about death, which may mean avoidance of facing the negative situation of death. Because loneliness and death anxiety are also related to serious mental problems in individuals. In addition to some negative psychological and physiological problems of loneliness in studies; self-hiding (Kelly & Achter, 1995) and anxiety (Larson & Chastain, 1990) show that alone individuals have difficulty in opening themselves up and this case also hinders the development of social relations (Öksüz, 2005). Therefore, as can be seen in the above-mentioned explanations, it seems that talking about death is more difficult in young people with low levels of loneliness.

Another finding in the study was that young people with high levels of meaning in life were not bothered to talk about death. In other words, talking about death can be important in terms of accepting death and dealing with the anxiety of death, and it is thought that meaning in life can have an important contribution. According to Frankl, the meaning of life is not only associated with the basic motivating force in human beings, as well as an effort to make sense or make sense of life (Frankl, 2010) but also associated with protective mental health components such as psychological well-being (Bonebright, Clay & Ankenmann, 2000) and loss and coping with mourning (Davis, Wortman, Lehman & Silver, 2000). In this context, it is indicated that developing an attitude towards the inevitable pain as a way of finding meaning in life, when faced with a hopeless or irrevocable fate, the individual may try to change himself and resist the pain if he cannot change the "situation" (Frankl, 2010). Kübler-Ross (1997) emphasizes that the person who integrates with the idea of death can lead a more meaningful life. In this sense, the fact that young people with high levels of meaning in life are not bothered to talk about death may be associated with the high level of meaning in life allowing them to cope with death anxiety easily and to accept death.

In the finding on the fourth sub-problem of the study, it is seen that there is a negative and meaningful relationship between death anxiety and meaning in life in young people; as the anxiety of death increases, the meaning of life appears to decrease. While meaning in life is associated with individuals' understanding their lives as satisfactory, and establishing relationships with other people and maintaining interpersonal relationships in a healthy way; low level of search for meaning is associated with difficulties in many areas, especially interpersonal relationships, inability to solve problems, inconsistency in self-perception and low self-esteem (Mushtaq et. al., 2014). Tomer and Eliason (2000) also associated the anxiety of death with the loss of meaning in

life; Frankl (2010), on the other hand, described the lack of meaning in life as meaninglessness. In the case of meaninglessness experienced as existential emptiness, boredom, recession and sense of emptiness, individual cannot find his direction and purpose, and does not know what he wants to do when he is free (Yalom, 2009). According to Das (1998), the meaning of life serves some functions in human life; it provides reasons for human survival, performs the function of control for events in life and enables the formation of self-value, many emotional problems are solved and life becomes valuable. Accordingly, while the high level of search for meaning in life in young people refers to a positive situation, low level or meaninglessness can be considered as associated with death anxiety.

In the study, a positive and significant correlation was found between loneliness and death anxiety; it was determined that, as the level of loneliness increases in young people, death anxiety also increases. This finding appears to have been supported by some studies in the literature revealing the positive relationship between loneliness and death anxiety (Adams et. al., 2004). Death anxiety is associated with emotional, cognitive, experimental, developmental and sociocultural factors as well as stressful environments, unpredictable conditions, diagnosis of a life-threatening disease or experiences of an event, or death and death experiences (Lehto & Stein, 2009). This finding is thought to be important in revealing the role of loneliness in understanding the dynamics of death anxiety in young people.

With regard to loneliness, it is indicated that low social support (Cicirelli, 2002) and physical and psychological health (Fortner, Neimeyer & Rybarczyk, 2000) are associated with death anxiety; that high level of social support has a protective role in the face of death anxiety (Pinson, 2010). There are also studies showing that high level of death anxiety together with loneliness associated with suicidal thoughts increases the risk of death (Steptoe, Shankar, Demakakos & Wardle, 2013). In the study conducted by Özdemir and Tatar (2019), it was determined that loneliness shows the strongest relationship with depression and anxiety. Accordingly, efforts to reduce the anxiety of loneliness and death can contribute both in terms of inter-variables relationship and in support of psychological well-being in young people.

In the other finding of the study, there is a negative and meaningful relationship between loneliness and meaning in life. Accordingly, as the loneliness levels of individuals increase, levels of meaning in life also decrease. This finding can be considered as reducing the level of loneliness in young people will contribute to the search for meaning in life. Among studies supporting this finding, also in a study conducted by Altınparmak and Deniz (2018), it was found out that there are negative significant relationships between existence of meaning in life and social emotional loneliness, romantic loneliness, family loneliness and social loneliness; that loneliness in social relations predicts the existence of meaning in life significantly. Loneliness is considered as a negative life experience for young people (Ernst & Cacioppo, 1999) in terms reduced ability to communicate with others, feeling abandoned, causing negative assessments of oneself and having negative consequences (Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2009); and loneliness is discussed with its aspect causing pain and feelings of inadequacy in

various studies (Perron, Cleverley & Kidd, 2014). In addition, loneliness in young people was found to be associated with suffering, humiliation, stigma and shame (Dahlberg, 2007); low levels of resilience and high psychological stress (Perron, Cleverley & Kidd, 2014). On the other hand, the existence of meaning in life as a positive condition in young people serves positive functions in human life. Thus, when people find meaning in their lives, many emotional problems are solved, and life becomes valuable (Das, 1998). Emmons (2005) emphasizes the importance of personal relationships and personal development, as well as intimacy, spirituality, among the variables that constitute the source of life's meaning and search for meaning. When these results are evaluated in general, it is thought that increasing the level of loneliness will pose a risk in terms of meaning in life as in many negative situations in young people.

In the finding of the fifth sub-problem of the study, loneliness and meaning in life significantly predicted the death anxiety. According to these results, as the level of meaning in life decreases in young people, death anxiety also increases; as the level of loneliness increases, the anxiety of death increases. It was determined that this finding is supported by the findings of some studies in the literature, and a relationship was revealed between lack of meaning in life and anxiety of death (Tomer & Eliason, 2000). The existence of meaning in life in an individual is associated with psychological health and positive emotions (Ryff & Singer, 1998); it is emphasized that individuals are more creative and prone to self-realization if they think they are living a meaningful life (Emmons, 2005). In this respect, the absence of meaning in life in young people may be effective in increasing the anxiety of death.

Another finding in the study reveals the positive relationship between loneliness and death anxiety (Tomer & Eliason, 2000; Pinson, 2010). Loneliness can lead young people to feelings of being alone in the world, thinking that their lives are aimless and useless, and experience feelings of emptiness and abandonment (Akgun, 2001). As the feeling of loneliness increases, the individual may feel more depressed and anxious (Colonna, Milica Nikolić, Vente & Bögels, 2017). There is a relationship between high anxiety of death and experiencing intense feelings of anger and hostility, it is indicated that death anxiety is at the center of panic disorders and depressive disorders (Iverach, Menzies & Menzies, 2014). The fact that loneliness is associated with anxiety, depression and other negative variables suggests that loneliness is an important variable in terms of mental health and death anxiety in young people. In this context, understanding the role of loneliness in adolescents may be important in terms of death anxiety.

When the findings are evaluated in general, death anxiety is discussed in association with negativity in the dimension of susceptibility to loneliness, depression and anxiety in individuals, weakening cognitive functions and increasing the risk of death (Lee & Ko, 2018). Accordingly, since death anxiety is an important variable in terms of understanding the nature of mental needs in young people as well as its relation to negativity, it can be clearly seen that the findings of this study will contribute to other studies.

5. Conclusion

In this study, loneliness in young people and meaning in life significantly predicted the death anxiety; there was a positive and meaningful relationship between death anxiety and loneliness, and a negative relationship was found between death anxiety and meaning in life. In the study, a negative significant relationship was found between loneliness and meaning in life. In addition, it was determined that, while death anxiety varied significantly depending on gender, the levels of meaning in life and loneliness did not differ significantly according to gender. It was determined that the majority of young people suffered at least one loss in the form of the death of a relative; there was not a significant difference in meaning in life, death anxiety and loneliness according to level of loss. In the study, it was found differed significantly levels of death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness depending on the state of being uncomfortable talking about death.

6. Suggestions

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are presented: In young people, being a university senior or graduate student, their level of readiness to transition to adult responsibilities and the stress and uncertainty in terms of finding a job make them more vulnerable in many areas. In this context, it will be important to study the death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness from the problem areas experienced by young people. The relationship between variables were emphasized in this study. In new studies, studies can be carried out to reveal the cause and effect relationship between variables. In addition, comparative studies can be carried out between groups of different age and socio-economic levels related to death anxiety, meaning in life and loneliness.

7. Limitations

It should be noted that the findings can only be generalized to the universe if this study as this research was carried out with young people at the higher education level in the university senior and graduate group.

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